

On the Role of Feasibility Sparsity in Federated Edge Service Placement

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Abstract—Federation across edge and cloud providers is a key enabler for flexible service deployment in future 6G systems. However, applications with strict latency requirements can only be placed on geographically proximate infrastructure, inducing sparse and heterogeneous resource feasibility constraints. In this paper, we study how this latency-induced sparsity impacts the benefits of federation. We formalize federated service placement as a latency-constrained multi-resource generalized assignment problem over a sparse feasibility graph, enabling us to isolate how feasible-set sparsity shapes the value of federation. We show that federation is most valuable when latency-feasible neighborhoods are small or unevenly distributed, and that this effect cannot be explained by aggregate capacity alone. Using population-driven spatial scenarios with heterogeneous infrastructure deployments, we demonstrate that federation provides the largest improvements when feasible sets are small and unevenly distributed. Our results highlight that the effectiveness of federation critically depends on geographic feasibility constraints.

Index Terms—edge federation, latency-constrained placement, multi-resource allocation, atomic application admission

I. INTRODUCTION

Future 6G infrastructures are expected to comprise geographically distributed, heterogeneous compute resources operated by multiple providers. By enabling resource sharing across administrative domains, federation has been widely considered as a means to improve utilization, reduce operational costs, and enhance service reliability. Prior work has primarily focused on optimizing resource allocation, admission control and economic incentives within such federated environments. In this line of work it is often assumed that resources are broadly accessible across the system.

However, new 6G use cases such as immersive reality, autonomous systems, and real-time digital twins are inherently latency-sensitive, imposing strict delay constraints on service placement. Under such requirements, each application component can only access a limited set of nearby facilities, so placement decisions are constrained not only by resource availability but also by geography. This induces a sparse and heterogeneous feasibility structure and its characteristics depend on the spatial distribution of demand and infrastructure which can lead to localized bottlenecks even when aggregate capacity is sufficient.

These observations raise a fundamental question: *what determines the value of federation under latency-constrained service placement?* We argue that the answer lies not only

in aggregate capacity, but also in the structure of latency-feasible assignment sets as well. In particular, the sparsity and distribution of these sets govern the extent to which federation can effectively expand placement options and alleviate bottlenecks. In this paper, we develop a framework to characterize this effect and show that federation gains are driven by feasibility sparsity and cross-provider diversity, rather than capacity alone.

To study this effect, we model service placement as a latency-constrained multi-dimensional generalized assignment problem with sparse feasibility structure.

Related Work: A large body of work studies service placement in heterogeneous edge computing systems, including joint placement and request scheduling over distributed resources with heterogeneous capacities and service demands [1], [2], differentiated resource constraints and allocation models [3]–[5], and approximation-based approaches with provable guarantees [6]. Together, these works establish heterogeneous service placement as a central optimization problem in edge computing [7], [8]. However, they typically formulate placement over broadly accessible infrastructure and do not treat latency-constrained feasible accessibility as a primary structural object.

A second line of work considers richer service and application models. Multi-component application placement was studied early as a way to represent applications with several deployable modules [9], while more recent works model edge applications as collaborative services, microservice systems, or graph-based structures [10]–[12]. Other studies extend placement to multi-objective settings by incorporating energy efficiency, QoS awareness, or reliability [13]–[15]. While this literature captures richer application semantics, it does not isolate how geographic latency constraints shape the feasible set of facilities available to each task.

A third line of work studies placement and orchestration in federated edge and cloud-edge environments. Early works focused on interoperability and coordinated provisioning across multiple providers [16], while later studies examined federated MEC placement and edge federation as architectural models for cross-domain deployment [17], [18]. Continuum-oriented approaches further consider QoS-aware orchestration and secure placement across cloud-edge infrastructures [19], [20]. In contrast, we study federated placement under strict

latency-feasibility constraints and show that federation gain is governed by the sparse structure of feasible assignment sets, rather than by aggregate capacity alone.

Contributions: This paper makes the following contributions:

- We identify *latency-induced feasibility sparsity* as a key structural factor governing the value of federation in edge service placement, showing that federation gains are not explained by aggregate capacity alone.
- We formulate federated service placement as a constrained multi-resource assignment problem over a sparse feasibility graph with atomic application admission, enabling isolation of sparse feasibility effects.
- We introduce a provider-level feasibility metric that captures cross-domain accessibility and show that it is a strong predictor of federation gain across heterogeneous spatial scenarios.
- Through spatially grounded experiments, we demonstrate that federation yields the largest improvements when feasible sets are small and fragmented across providers, and that these gains diminish as cross-provider accessibility increases.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a federated 6G edge infrastructure with geographically distributed computing facilities serving latency-sensitive applications. Placement is governed by spatial deployment, heterogeneous resource capacities, and latency-constrained feasibility across facilities operated by different providers. Fig. 1 illustrates a toy instance with two providers, multiple facilities, and three applications, showing how latency constraints induce sparse feasible assignment sets and how federation expands them across provider boundaries.

Fig. 1. Toy instance of the system model. Two providers P_1, P_2 operate geographically distributed facilities f_1, f_2, \dots, f_6 of different classes (cloud, edge, micro-edge). Applications A_1, A_2, A_3 are anchored at different locations, each consisting of multiple required tasks. For each task, only a subset of nearby facilities is feasible (i.e. $\mathcal{F}(t_{12}) = \{f_3\}, \mathcal{F}(t_{21}) = \{f_2, f_4\}$). In the non-federated regime, tasks can use only feasible facilities of their home provider ($\mathcal{F}(t_{21}) = \{f_4\}, \mathcal{F}(t_{13}) = \{f_1, f_2, f_3\}$).

Facilities, Providers, and Applications: Let \mathcal{P} denote the set of providers and \mathcal{F} the set of facilities. Each facility $f \in \mathcal{F}$ is owned by a provider $o(f) \in \mathcal{P}$, located at $p_f \in \mathbb{R}^2$, and characterized by a multi-resource capacity vector $\mathbf{C}_f \in \mathbb{R}_+^R$ and a per-unit resource cost vector $\alpha_f \in \mathbb{R}_+^R$. We consider 6G resource described by the set $\mathcal{R} = [r_1, r_2, \dots, r_R]$. Facilities may belong to different infrastructure classes (e.g., cloud, edge, micro-edge), reflecting heterogeneous deployment, cost, and processing-delay characteristics.

Let \mathcal{A} denote the set of application requests. Each application $a \in \mathcal{A}$ is associated with an anchor location $p_a \in \mathbb{R}^2$, a class $c(a) \in \mathcal{C}$, a home provider $o(a) \in \mathcal{P}$, and a set of required tasks \mathcal{T}_a . The anchor location represents the geographic point of service delivery during the placement interval. Each task $t \in \mathcal{T}_a$ has resource demand vector $\mathbf{d}_t \in \mathbb{R}_+^R$ and latency requirement $L_t > 0$. All tasks in \mathcal{T}_a must be placed for an application to be successfully deployed.

Utility and Cost: Applications of the same class share a common utility u_a . Assigning task t to facility f incurs cost

$$c_{tf} = \sum_{r=1}^R \alpha_f^r d_t^r. \quad (1)$$

We adopt class-based utility, fixed anchors, and atomic admission to isolate the structural effect of interest: the accessibility of latency-feasible infrastructure. Class-based utilities capture service priority without introducing application-specific valuation assumptions; fixed anchors model the geographic demand point during a placement interval; and atomic admission reflects services whose value is realized only when all required components are deployed. We adopt a bundled task model rather than an explicitly interconnected graph, as it captures applications whose components can be deployed independently with limited interdependence, allowing us to isolate the impact of latency-constrained feasibility on placement decisions.

Latency-Constrained Feasibility: For application a and facility f , end-to-end latency is

$$\ell_{af} = \ell^{\text{PROP}}(p_a, p_f) + \ell_f^{\text{PROC}}, \quad (2)$$

where $\ell^{\text{PROP}}(p_a, p_f)$ is the propagation delay between anchor and facility and ℓ_f^{PROC} is a facility-dependent processing delay. A facility is feasible for task $t \in \mathcal{T}_a$ if

$$\ell_{af} \leq L_t, \quad (3)$$

which defines the feasible set

$$\mathcal{F}(t) = \{f \in \mathcal{F} \mid \ell_{af} \leq L_t\}. \quad (4)$$

To distinguish local and federated placement, we define $\mathcal{F}_{\text{loc}}(t) = \{f \in \mathcal{F}(t) \mid o(f) = o(a)\}$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\text{fed}}(t) = \mathcal{F}(t)$. Thus, federation does not change latency feasibility itself; it enlarges the set of feasible assignments by allowing tasks to use latency-feasible facilities across providers.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Given a set of applications \mathcal{A} and facilities \mathcal{F} , the system decides which applications to admit and how to assign their tasks to facilities subject to latency-feasibility and resource-capacity constraints. Since feasibility is precomputed through the sets $\mathcal{F}(t)$, the optimization is defined only over latency-feasible task–facility pairs.

Let $y_a \in \{0, 1\}$ indicate whether application $a \in \mathcal{A}$ is admitted, and let $x_{tf} \in \{0, 1\}$ indicate whether task t is assigned to facility $f \in \mathcal{F}(t)$. The placement problem is formulated as:

$$\max_{\{x_{tf}\}, \{y_a\}} \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} u_a y_a - \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}_a} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}(t)} c_{tf} x_{tf} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}(t)} x_{tf} = y_a, \quad \forall a \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}_a \quad (8a)$$

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}: f \in \mathcal{F}(t)} d_t^r x_{tf} \leq C_f^r, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F}, r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (8b)$$

$$x_{tf} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad y_a \in \{0, 1\}. \quad (8c)$$

The objective in (5) maximizes the net benefit of admitted applications. The first term captures the utility obtained when an application is admitted, while the second term accounts for the operational cost of placing its tasks on heterogeneous facilities.

Constraint (8a) enforces atomic admission. If application a is admitted, every task in \mathcal{T}_a must be placed exactly once on a feasible facility. If a is not admitted, none of its tasks can be assigned. Constraint (8b) enforces facility capacity limits in every resource dimension. The total demand of all tasks assigned to facility f cannot exceed the available capacity of that facility. Constraint (8c) defines the binary nature of the decision variables. Variable x_{tf} indicates whether task t is assigned to facility f , and variable y_a indicates whether application a is admitted.

The formulation is a multi-dimensional generalized assignment problem with atomic group constraints, restricted to a latency-feasible assignment graph. Its distinctive feature is that the optimization is not defined over all task and facility pairs, but only over the sparse feasible sets induced by geography and latency.

Federated and Non-Federated Placement The formulation above applies to both non-federated and federated deployment. The difference lies in the feasible assignment sets available to each task.

In the non-federated regime, each application belongs to a home domain, and each task t may only be assigned to latency-feasible facilities within that domain. Denoting this restricted feasible set by $\mathcal{F}^{\text{loc}}(t)$, the optimization is carried out over local feasible assignments only.

In the federated regime, tasks may be assigned to any participating provider, as long as latency constraints are satisfied. The feasible set then expands to $\mathcal{F}^{\text{fed}}(t)$, with

$$\mathcal{F}^{\text{loc}}(t) \subseteq \mathcal{F}^{\text{fed}}(t).$$

Hence, federation does not alter the optimization structure itself but enlarges the assignment neighborhood of each task by exposing additional feasible facilities across domains. The benefit of federation therefore depends on how constrained the original local feasible sets are.

Feasibility Sparsity Metrics To quantify the structure of latency-feasible assignment sets, we introduce two simple metrics capturing their size and cross-provider diversity.

Facility-level sparsity. For each task $t \in \mathcal{T}$, let $F(t)$ denote its set of latency-feasible facilities. We define the average feasible-set size as

$$\bar{F} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{T}|} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} |F(t)|. \quad (6)$$

Lower values of \bar{F} indicate stronger feasibility sparsity, i.e., tasks have fewer placement options.

Provider-level feasibility diversity. Let $P(t) = \{o(f) \mid f \in F(t)\}$ denote the set of providers reachable by task t . We define

$$\bar{P} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{T}|} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} |P(t)|. \quad (7)$$

This metric captures how many distinct provider domains are accessible under latency constraints.

While \bar{F} measures how many feasible facilities are available, \bar{P} captures whether these options are distributed across independent providers. As we show in Section VI, this distinction is critical for understanding federation gain.

IV. COMPUTATIONAL HARDNESS AND EXPERIMENTAL SOLVER

The allocation problem in Section III is a combinatorial assignment problem with three coupled features: multi-resource capacity constraints, assignment restrictions induced by latency-feasible sets, and atomic admission of whole applications. Since the purpose of this paper is to study how feasibility sparsity shapes federation gain, rather than to develop a new approximation algorithm, we use a simple scalable solver that remains faithful to these structural constraints.

Computational Hardness: The placement problem in Section III is NP-hard. This follows directly from a reduction to the multiple knapsack problem in a simplified setting with a single resource, one task per application, and unrestricted feasibility. Hence, even without latency constraints or atomic bundles, the problem reduces to selecting and assigning items to capacity-constrained facilities, which is NP-hard [6]. We omit the full reduction due to space limitation.

Greedy Allocation Heuristic: Since exact optimization becomes intractable for the large instances considered in Section V, we employ a simple greedy heuristic that respects latency feasibility and atomic admission.

Applications are processed in decreasing order of a utility-to-demand score

$$s_a = \frac{w_{c(a)} - C_a^{\min}}{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}_a} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} d_t^r / C_r^{\text{tot}}}, \quad (8)$$

where C_a^{\min} is the minimum feasible placement cost of application a , obtained by assigning each task to the lowest-cost facility in its feasible set.

Given this ordering, each application is considered atomically. For each task $t \in \mathcal{T}_a$, the algorithm selects the lowest-cost facility in $\mathcal{F}(t)$ with sufficient residual capacity. If all tasks can be placed, the application is admitted and capacities are updated; otherwise, it is rejected.

This heuristic preserves the two key structural elements of the model: assignments are restricted to latency-feasible sets, and admission is atomic. It is therefore suitable for evaluating how feasibility sparsity affects federation gain.

We use this heuristic because it preserves the mechanism studied in this paper while remaining computationally lightweight.

To verify that this simplification is adequate for comparative analysis, Section VI compares the greedy allocator against exact optimization on small instances and shows that it tracks the optimal welfare trend closely over the parameter ranges considered. The greedy solver is then used for the large-scale experiments where exact optimization is impractical.

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We evaluate the model on stylized spatial instances generated over a normalized population-density field derived from WorldPop [21]. Let

$$pd(x) = \frac{\text{density}(x)}{\max_{y \in \mathcal{X}} \text{density}(y)}, \quad x \in \mathcal{X}, \quad (9)$$

where \mathcal{X} denotes the geographical region. This field is used as an exogenous spatial signal for both infrastructure deployment and application demand, so that geography directly shapes the induced feasible assignment structure.

A. Supply, Demand, and Feasibility

Infrastructure consists of three facility classes, $\mathcal{M} = \{\text{CLOUD}, \text{EDGE}, \text{MICRO}\}$, representing remote cloud, metropolitan edge, and dispersed micro-edge resources. Facilities are placed according to class-dependent threshold rules over $pd(x)$: cloud toward low-density regions, edge toward dense urban regions, and micro-edge more diffusely over populated areas. Each class $m \in \mathcal{M}$ is assigned a base capacity vector \bar{C}_m , a per-resource cost vector $\bar{\alpha}_m$, and a processing delay τ_m . The baseline facility-count ratio is $N_{\text{CLOUD}} : N_{\text{EDGE}} : N_{\text{MICRO}} = 2 : 10 : 20$.

Application demand consists of three classes, $\mathcal{C} = \{\text{V2X}, \text{FACTORY}, \text{HOLO}\}$, chosen to span different combinations of spatial concentration, latency criticality, and resource intensity. Anchors are sampled from class-dependent rules over $pd(x)$: holographic services are concentrated in dense urban regions, V2X demand is urban-centered but more dispersed, and factory demand is more common in low- and medium-density areas. Each class $c \in \mathcal{C}$ is assigned a utility weight w_c and a fixed bundle of mandatory tasks T_c , with task demands defined over $\mathcal{R} = \{\text{NET}, \text{CPU}, \text{GPU}, \text{RAM}\}$. $\ell_{prop}(p_a, p_f)$ is computed as the Euclidean between app

and infrastructure distance using a constant propagation-speed approximation. This construction generates controlled mixtures of tight and loose feasible neighborhoods across service classes.

B. Instance Generation and Evaluation Regimes

Instances are generated sequentially by sampling application classes, drawing anchor locations, and instantiating their task bundles until a target congestion level is reached:

$$\eta = \max_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \frac{D_r}{C_r}, \quad (10)$$

where D_r and C_r denote total demand and total capacity in resource dimension r .

To define provider ownership, facilities are partitioned into *three* (3) providers after placement using K -means over facility locations. Each application is then assigned to the nearest provider region. We compare two regimes: *non-federated* placement, where tasks are restricted to their home provider's latency-feasible facilities, and *federated* placement, where tasks may use any latency-feasible facility. Thus, federation changes the feasible assignment neighborhoods available to tasks, but not the underlying allocation problem.

The main experimental knobs are: i) *scale*, through the total number of facilities, ii) *relative load*, through the target congestion level η and iii) *spatial heterogeneity*, through the overlap between supply-side and demand-side placement rules. These knobs directly shape the size and provider diversity of feasible sets. For small instances, we compare the heuristic against the exact optimization model while for larger instances, we report heuristic results only.

VI. RESULTS

We evaluate the proposed federated placement framework through controlled experiments that isolate the effects of congestion and spatial restructuring. Rather than simply confirming that federation improves performance, we use these experiments to identify which structural properties of latency-feasible assignment sets govern the magnitude of this improvement. We interpret the results using the feasibility metrics defined in Section III-B.

A. Impact of Federation Under Congestion

Fig. 2 shows that federation consistently improves both welfare and admission across the entire congestion range, with the gap increasing as load rises. For example, at $\eta \approx 1.2$, federated placement achieves a normalized welfare of approximately 3.0, compared to about 1.7 for the non-federated scheme, corresponding to a relative improvement of over 70%. A similar gap appears in admission rate, where federation maintains roughly 0.65 while the non-federated scheme drops below 0.4.

These results confirm that federation becomes more valuable as congestion increases, since it enables the system to utilize capacity that would otherwise remain stranded in isolated provider domains. At the same time, the bottom-left panel shows that the greedy solver closely tracks the optimal trend

Fig. 2. Impact of congestion on allocation performance. From left to right and top to bottom: normalized welfare, admission rate, runtime, and utilization.

on small instances while remaining significantly faster, justifying its use in the larger experiments below.

B. Impact of Spatial Restructuring

We next examine how spatial structure affects federation gain by interpolating between heterogeneous and uniform deployments using the parameter $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, while fixing $\eta = 0.8$.

The parameter α controls the degree to which both infrastructure placement and application demand follow the underlying population density field. When $\alpha = 0$, facilities and demand are placed according to the original heterogeneous rules, resulting in strong spatial concentration and mismatches between supply and demand. As α increases, both are progressively smoothed toward a uniform spatial distribution, reducing geographic skew. Thus, α does not directly affect resource capacity or workload, but reshapes the spatial alignment between supply and demand, and consequently the structure of latency-feasible sets.

Fig. 3 shows that while federated placement consistently outperforms the non-federated scheme, the *magnitude* of the gain varies significantly with α . In particular, the relative normalized welfare gain (bottom-right) ranges from approximately 0.4 to 0.8 and exhibits a clear non-monotonic pattern.

The bottom-left panel explains this behavior. The average number of feasible facilities per task, \bar{F} , varies between roughly 22 and 24 as α changes, indicating that spatial restructuring modifies the size of latency-feasible neighborhoods.

Comparing the two panels reveals that federation gain is largest when \bar{F} is smaller, *i.e.*, when feasible sets are more

Fig. 3. Impact of spatial restructuring through the uniformity parameter α . From left to right and top to bottom: normalized welfare, admission rate, average feasible facilities per task, and relative welfare gain of federation.

Fig. 4. Relative welfare gain of federation versus average feasible providers per task across all scenarios. Each point corresponds to one scenario instance and is colored by the spatial uniformity parameter α .

restrictive. Parameter α influences performance through the structure of feasible assignment sets rather than through uniformity itself. However, the variation in \bar{F} alone does not fully explain the observed gains, suggesting that the distribution of feasible options across providers must also be taken into account.

C. Provider-Level Feasibility as the Main Structural Predictor

To directly identify the relevant structural quantity, we relate federation gain to the provider-level feasibility metric \bar{P} across all scenarios.

Fig. 4 reveals a strong negative relationship between federation gain and \bar{P} . As \bar{P} increases, the relative welfare gain drops from values above 1.0 to below 0.3. This trend is consistent across all spatial configurations, as indicated by the color distribution over α .

The statistical strength of this relationship is high, with Pearson correlation $r = -0.77$ and Spearman correlation $\rho = -0.76$, indicating that provider-level feasible diversity is a robust predictor of federation gain.

This result clarifies why \bar{F} alone is insufficient. While \bar{F} measures how many facilities are available, it does not capture whether these facilities belong to different providers. Federation operates across provider domains, so its benefit depends on whether latency-feasible options span multiple independent capacity pools. *When \bar{P} is low, feasible facilities are concentrated within few providers, and federation significantly expands the effective assignment space. When \bar{P} is already high, much of this flexibility is already present, and the additional benefit of federation is limited.*

Taken together, these results indicate that federation gain is closely tied to the structure of latency-feasible assignment sets, motivating a more general interpretation discussed next.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper examined the role of latency-induced feasibility structure in federated edge service placement. We showed that the benefit of federation is not determined by aggregate capacity or spatial uniformity alone, but by the structure of latency-feasible assignment sets. In particular, spatial restructuring affects performance through its impact on facility-level sparsity, while the resulting welfare gain is primarily governed by provider-level feasible diversity. Among the metrics considered, the average number of feasible providers per task is as the most informative predictor of federation gain. These findings suggest that the value of federation is greater when feasible assignments are fragmented across provider domains, and naturally diminishes when cross-provider accessibility is already high.

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